

REGIONAL DETAILS OF THE DEMOGRAPHIC SITUATION OF TASHKENT REGION

Annotation. This article describes demographic processes and their impact on society. In particular, the article examines changes in the composition of the population of Tashkent region, population reproduction, birth and death and its effect on population growth. In addition, regional aspects of the demographic situation of the population of the region and the reasons for their changes were analyzed.

Key words: demographic process, population birth, death, natural reproduction, population movement, marriage and divorce, village, city.

INTRODUCTION. Tashkent region in the republic has its own demographic potential according to separately separate standing from the regions one is considered Province population the number according to Samarkand, Farg'ana, Kashkadarya in our country and Andijan from the regions then, the country constant 8.7 percent of the population share with fifth occupied the rank. In the province of the country all regions such as population the number increased is going 2010-2020 in the interval his population of 33-35 thousand on average every year to the person increased that he went or of the population average yearly increase of 1.3 percent organize what he did we say can _ Population dynamics in Tashkent region it can be observed that the number of growth, birth and death processes has changed significantly compared to previous years.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. The population and related demographic processes have always been the focus of attention of scientists. A. Sauvy in France, E. Cole in the USA, and A. Ya. Boyarsky, J. Bourgeois-Pich and others conducted their demographic research in the territory of the former USSR. A number of scientists have conducted scientific research in this regard in Uzbekistan. At this point, it is appropriate to mention the works of scientists such as M.Karakhanov, R.Mullajonov, O.Ata- Mirzayev, A.Qayumov, A.Soliyev, M. Boriyeva, Z.Tojiyeva, Kh.Mamadaliyeva, S.Zokirov, who carried out scientific research in the field of demography in our country.

RESULTS. The geographical location of the province, in turn, indicates the diversity of its ethnic and national composition. This, in turn, has a significant impact on the number and dynamics of the population within the national structure.

As of January 1, 2010, the permanent population of the region was 2585.9 thousand people, and in the corresponding period of 2021 it reached 2975.9

thousand people. Population for ten years absolute growth of 390 thousand people organize reached _ When analyzing the population by regions, we can see that as of January 1, 2021, the number of rural residents (1506.0 thousand people) was higher than the urban population (1469.9 thousand people). As of January 2021, Yangiyol district has the largest population of 209,900 people, followed by Kibrau district with 202,200 people and Zangiota district with 195,400 people., 191.3 thousand people in Angren city, 183.2 thousand people in Tashkent district, 171.2 thousand people in Bostonliq district, 162.8 thousand people in Chirchik city, 159.5 thousand people in Bekobod district, 157.5 thousand people in Parkent district, 142.5 thousand people in Ortachirchik district, 138.9 thousand people in Urychirchik district, 136.1 thousand people in Chinoz district, 133.4 thousand people in Almalyk city, 127.5 thousand people in Boka district, 110.1 people in Kuyichirchik district thousand people, 106.4 thousand people in Akkurgan district, 102.0 thousand people in Piskent district, 96.9 thousand people in Bekobod city, 97 thousand people in Ohangaron district, 61.7 thousand people in Yangiyol city, 51 in Nurafshan city 4,000 people, and 39,000 people in the city of Ohangaron. Yangiyol district has the largest population in terms of cities and districts, 209,900 people, Kibrai district has 202,200 people, and the largest population in cities is 191,300 people. Occupied by Angren. Most less population the number Iron man in the district note done in which 39.0 thousand _ population residence to do was determined. The share of women and men in the permanent population of the region is equally distributed, and representatives of both sexes have a share of 50 percent of the total population.

Births in Tashkent region in 2020 number of 65,954 people organize reached in it girl children (34,028) weight boy from the number of children (31,926). a little more organize reached in Tashkent region alive born the number is 65.9 thousand

Picture-1. Births in Tashkent region in 2020 girl and son children weight

Source: Gender statistics based on the author by was built.

someone organize reached and died those who have number is 18.4 thousand note done Scientist degree January-December 2020 18,400 per month organize did and that's it for 2019 2365 compared to the period (16035). increased Suitable respectively scientist the coefficient is 6.2 ppm organize (in 2019 5.5 per thousand in January-December). The dead number increase Zangiota (from 4.9 to 7.1 per thousand), Qibray (from 5.5 to 7.1 per thousand), Tashkent (from 5.1 to 7.3 per thousand) districts the most a lot observed if only Bekobod (5.8 to 5.5 per thousand) and In the cities of Ohangaron (7.2 to 5.7 per thousand). drop off tendency observed

Province on the hundred in 2020 gave total scientist 18,400 cases organize reached Attention owner aspect it is of the region all in the regions (Yangiyol from the city except) death in cases Women weight significantly different than men. In 2020, the total number of female deaths in Tashkent region was 10,091, while the number of male deaths was 8,309. This trend was observed not only in 2020, but also in previous years. In comparison, men accounted for more deaths in 2011-2013, while women had higher mortality rates from 2014 to January 1, 2021. We wrote above that despite the fact that the weight of women at birth is higher than that of men, men are generally more than women. We think that the fact that the number of deaths among women is higher than that of men will clarify the matter.

In 2020, a total of 26,122 marriages were recorded by FXDYO authorities in Tashkent region, of which 10,537 were in cities and 15,585 in villages. Yangiyol (1826), Qibray (1796) and Zangiota districts (1707) had the highest number of marriages, while Nurafshan (391) and Ohangaron (252) cities recorded the lowest number of marriages in the region. For comparison, in 2018, Yangiyol (1,722), Qibray (1,606) and Zangiota districts (1,591) had the highest number of registered marriages, Nurafshan (351) and Ohangaron (1,090) relatively many marriages were recorded in ta) cities.

A total of 2,958 divorce cases were observed in Tashkent region in 2020, of which 1,536 occurred in cities and 1,422 in villages. The analysis of divorce events is also important in the assessment of demographic processes, because the separation of parents is not reflected in the reproductive health of children. 51.3% of the total divorces recorded in the region in 2020 occurred between childless couples, 28.5% occurred in families with one child, and 20.2% occurred in families with two or more children. As usual, Kibray district (285), Yangiyol district (204) and Chirchik city (241) are in the first place in terms of the awards. Nurafshan city (51), Ohangaron city (56) and Piskent districts (56) have the smallest share in the total number of rulings.

According to comparative analysis, it was found that the number of marriages is several times higher than that of divorces. The largest share of marriages fell on the share of Yangiyol and Qibray districts, while the Kibray district and Chirchik city are at the forefront of divorces. The fact that the numbers are higher than in other regions of the region can be explained by the fact that most of the population of the region lives in these regions.

The number of people who moved to the region in 2020 is 30 There were 791 people. For comparison, in 2010, this indicator was 15,467 people, and in 2015, it was 18,575 people. We can see that the numbers have doubled in ten years. The main reasons for the emigration are not clearly stated in the sources. The number of immigrants was in Chirchik city (6,178 people), Zangiota district (2,448 people), Yangiyol district (2,922 people) and Ukurenchirchik district (2,531 people). These regions are considered leaders in the region in terms of the number of immigrants.

Conclusion. In the Tashkent region, the birth rate among the local population is much higher, especially compared to the European population. The number of births in families belonging to local ethnicities - Uzbek, Kyrgyz, Tajik, is much higher than in the Russian-speaking population, and this can be explained by the historical tradition of large children, national customs. The number of children in the families of Bostonliq and Qibray districts, which have a relatively low birth rate, is due to the fact that there are more representatives of other nationalities than in other districts. 12% of the population of the above districts belong to representatives of other nationalities.

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